

Effect of Film Thickness on the Kinetics of Lithium Insertion in LiMn_2O_4 Films Made by Multilayer Pulsed Laser Deposition for Thin-Film All-Solid-State Battery Cathode Materials**

Collins Erinwingbovo,^[a] Valerie Siller,^[b] Marc Nuñez,^[b] Rafael Trócoli,^[c] Dorian Brogioli,^[a] Albert Tarancón,^[b, d] Alejandro Morata,^{*,[b]} and Fabio La Mantia^{*,[a]}

Multi-layer pulsed laser deposition is a promising technique for producing LiMn_2O_4 thin films for solid-state batteries. In this work, thin films are deposited with different numbers of pulses, leading to different thicknesses and grain sizes. We investigated “in operando” the kinetics of the Li^+ transfer into LiMn_2O_4 films by means of dynamic impedance spectroscopy. This technique allowed us to resolve the contributions of the reaction mechanism and of the transport phenomena, as well as to

quantify their equivalent resistances. Surprisingly, with increasing film thickness, the charge transfer resistance increases while the apparent diffusion coefficient of lithium increases, leading to a decrease of the mass transport resistance. It appears that both these effects are related to the dimension of the crystals in the LiMn_2O_4 thin films. These results provide new insights for an optimal tuning of the materials’ preparation in view of maximizing their electrochemical performances.

Introduction

Thin film micro-batteries are attracting interest due to their promising prospects in technologies such as sensors, medical implantable and wearable solutions, radio frequency identification tags, smart cards, and micro-electromechanical systems.^[1,2] This has led to the development of thin film cathode materials (V_2O_5 , LiFePO_4 , LiCoO_2 and LiMn_2O_4) produced with various methodologies such as chemical vapour deposition,^[3,4] sputtering,^[2,5] spray pyrolysis,^[6,7] and laser deposition.^[8,9] An advantage of thin films is the possibility to achieve improved electrochemical performance by controlling phase and micro-

structure of the films tuning deposition parameters, such as target composition,^[10] substrate temperature,^[11,12] oxygen pressure,^[13] or fluence.^[14]

Spinel LiMn_2O_4 (LMO) is one of the most promising candidates for thin film cathode materials due to its cost-effectiveness, environmental friendliness, high energy density, high power density, and high rate capability.^[15,16] LiMn_2O_4 films made by multi-layer pulsed laser deposition (PLD) have been reported as promising cathode materials due to their outstanding electrochemical performance,^[17,18] exhibiting a coulombic efficiency of 99.996% for over 3500 cycles while cycling at 348 C, with high specific power and specific energy.^[19] Trócoli et al. reported a dual ion battery consisting of LiMn_2O_4 films made with multi-layer PLD as the cathode and a zinc anode in a mixed aqueous electrolyte of Zn and Li ions, showing a coulombic efficiency of more than 99.94%.^[20] The power and energy requirement of the intended application dictates the thickness and density of the deposited thin films. An increase in the thickness of the film often results in a decrease in power density. This is a critical challenge in the development of a microbattery that can offer both high energy density and power density. For optimization of batteries for high energy and/or high power applications, a better understanding of the effect of film thickness on the kinetics of the Li^+ ion transfer in LiMn_2O_4 thin films is required to tailor materials development for better electrochemical performance. Tang and co-workers also investigated the kinetics of Li^+ in LiMn_2O_4 with cyclic voltammetry, potentiostatic intermittent titration technique, and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy and reported apparent diffusion coefficient in the range from 10^{-12} to 10^{-10} $\text{cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$.^[21] Park and co-workers have shown an increase in volume expansion/compression for thicker films^[22] and Liu et al. observed a 7.5% increase in capacity loss per cycle as LiMn_2O_4 film thickness increases.^[23] The possibility to enhance the

[a] Dr. C. Erinwingbovo, Dr. D. Brogioli, Prof. F. La Mantia
 Universität Bremen
 Energiespeicher- und Energiewandlersysteme
 Bibliothekstr. 1, 28359 Bremen (Germany)
 E-mail: lamantia@uni-bremen.de
 Homepage: www.esecs.uni-bremen.de

[b] Dr. V. Siller, Dr. M. Nuñez, Prof. A. Tarancón, Dr. A. Morata
 IREC
 Jardins de les Dones de Negre 1, 2a
 08930 Sant Adrià de Besòs, Barcelona (Spain)
 E-mail: amorata@irec.cat
 Homepage: www.atlab.es

[c] Dr. R. Trócoli
 Institut de Ciència de Materials de Barcelona (ICMAB-CSIC)
 Campus UAB
 Bellaterra, Catalonia, E-08193 (Spain)

[d] Prof. A. Tarancón
 ICREA
 Passeig de Lluís Companys 23, 08010 Barcelona (Spain)

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electrochemical performance of these films by structural engineering has also been illustrated by Hendriks et al.^[24]

Recently, we reported that the ion transfer mechanism of Li^+ from solution into $LiMn_2O_4$ films made by multi-layer PLD comprises of: (i) a surface adsorption process from the solution, likely involving the (de)solvation of the Li^+ together with other possible surface phenomena; and (ii) the reversible insertion of Li^+ into $LiMn_2O_4$.^[25] Bulk phenomena also affect the overall process, namely the diffusion of Li^+ in the $LiMn_2O_4$ lattice together with the diffusion and the migration of ions in the liquid solution. The mentioned study was performed on $LiMn_2O_4$ thin films, made by a multi-layer PLD approach. Using a similar analysis, in this paper, samples obtained with a different number of pulses are compared. They differ in mass loading, grain size and thickness; since the various properties are correlated, we use the measured thickness as the characteristic parameter. This work is partially reported in the Ph.D. thesis of one of the Authors.^[26] The differences between the samples in terms of kinetics of the Li^+ ion transfer are investigated using dynamic multi-frequency analysis (DMFA). This technique allows for direct investigation and observation of physico-chemical processes and phenomena while the system is evolving.^[27,28]

Results and Discussion

Structural characterization

We deposited LMO films by multi-layer PLD on $Si|TiN|Pt$ substrates. The analyzed samples are deposited with 30, 80, and 130 pulses, obtaining different thicknesses.

Figure 1 shows the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) micrograph of the top view and cross-section of the various LMO films. In all films, randomly oriented columnar grains were

observed. The SEM image indicates a change in the microstructure of the film: with increasing thickness, larger crystals appear, also leading to higher porosity. SEM images indicate the layers had a thickness of 190 nm, 340 nm, and 1070 nm for the application of 30, 80, and 130 pulses, respectively. In the following, the three samples will be identified by their measured thickness, although they also differ in various features, such as grain size and porosity. The analysis of the same materials was partially reported in the Ph.D. thesis of one of the Authors.^[26] In that document, the samples were identified by the thickness that was theoretically evaluated from the number of pulses, rather than by the actual thickness measured by SEM.

The X-ray diffraction patterns of the various LMO films are shown in Figure 2. The diffraction peak associated with $LiMn_2O_4$ spinel (JCPDS 00–035–782), which occurs at 18.6° , was observed in the films indicating that all films were composed by $LiMn_2O_4$.

Electrochemical results

The voltammogram obtained for the $LiMn_2O_4$ films, with a voltage sweep of 16 mVs^{-1} , in $1\text{ M Li}_2\text{SO}_4$, is shown in Figure 3. Well defined peak pairs (A and B during positive scan and A' and B' during the negative scan) are present in all the films. These peak pairs have been attributed to the Li^+ ion transfer into two solid solutions with different chemical potential of lithium (μ_{Li}).^[29,30]

The peak current in the voltammogram increases with increasing film thickness, due to an increase in active material per unit area as the film thickness increases. The specific capacity of the films increases by increasing the film thickness from $4.7\ \mu\text{Ah cm}^{-2}$ in 190 nm film, to $23.4\ \mu\text{Ah cm}^{-2}$ in 340 nm film, and $69.4\ \mu\text{Ah cm}^{-2}$ in 1070 nm film. According to the scan

Figure 1. SEM micrographs of deposited $LiMn_2O_4$ layers with (a-c) 190 nm, (d-f) 340 nm and (g-i) 1070 nm.

Figure 2. X-ray diffractogram of LiMn_2O_4 layers at different thicknesses (indicated by the subscript "LMO", in nm), compared to the response from the Si|TiN|Pt substrate. Black lines correspond to spinel LiMn_2O_4 (JCPDS 00-035-0782) and red dashed lines indicate Mn_3O_4 (JCPDS 00-024-0734) as a secondary phase.

Figure 3. Voltammogram obtained from the quasi-triangular wave applied to 190 nm (black line), 340 nm (red line), and 1070 nm (blue line) LiMn_2O_4 film in 1 M Li_2SO_4 solution at a scan rate of 16 mV s^{-1} .

rate, each scan lasts 50 s for all the samples. The peak currents observed in the three films are 2.5, 13.9, and 18.7 mA cm^{-2} ; keeping such currents during galvanostatic cycling would lead to C-rates of 530 C, 590 C, and 270 C, for the 190 nm, 340 nm, and 1070 nm films, respectively. The comparison between results of cyclic voltammetry and galvanostatic cycling is however not straightforward.

Figure 4 shows the dynamic impedance spectra obtained by DMFA. The potential of the LiMn_2O_4 films is driven with a combination of a quasi-triangular wave (approximately representing a cyclic voltammetry) and multi-sine; the impedance is

Figure 4. Nyquist plot of impedance spectra obtained in 1 M Li_2SO_4 within the frequency range of 210 kHz to 2.5 Hz at different potentials for LiMn_2O_4 films of different thickness. (a, b) 190 nm during negative and positive scan, respectively; (c, d) 340 nm during negative and positive scan, respectively; (e, f) 1070 nm during negative and positive scan, respectively. The symbols and the lines represent the experimental data and the data from the model, respectively.

monitored during both the negative and positive scans and for the various film thicknesses.

The resulting spectra present two semi-circles, representing two RC time constants, terminated by a straight line which occurs at an angle of less than 90° , attributed to solid-state diffusion of Li^+ in LiMn_2O_4 .^[25] The dynamic impedance spectra thus suggest a two-stage reversible process: (i) the (de)adsorption process possibly involving the (de)solvation of lithium in solution and (ii) the (de)insertion process of the adsorbed lithium ions into the LiMn_2O_4 .^[25] The first process, the (de)adsorption, is described as an equilibrium between lithium in solution, phase ε , and at the interface, phase i (Eq. 1):

This process, macroscopically observed as an adsorption, could be microscopically constituted by a loss of solvent molecules taking place when the ion is captured at the surface of the material, in the electric double layer; other adsorption

phenomena could also play a role. Since this process involves the crossing of a potential barrier, it will be modelled with an Arrhenius-like equation, bearing similarities with the Butler-Volmer equation.

The second process, the (de)insertion, is described as an equilibrium between the lithium at the interface and lithium in the lattice. The insertion takes place in two separate stages, giving rise to the couple of current peaks observed in the cyclic voltammetry (Figure 3). By using the primitive cell of the $LiMn_2O_4$ consisting of 14 atoms,^[25,31] the reactions are the following (Eqs. 2 and 3):

It is worth noting that it is unlikely that the physical origin of the first step can be attributed to the presence of a solid electrolyte interphase, which should consist of a mixed organic/inorganic matrix,^[32,33] or to a passivation layer. We mainly discard these hypotheses due to the fact that the resistance of the first step, that we named R_{ad} , is changing during the cycling of a factor 5–10. If the origin of such resistance were the presence of a passive layer of any nature, we would expect an almost constant resistance, or maybe slightly growing with the number of cycles.

This physical model gives rise to the equivalent circuit shown in Figure 5, which was used to fit the measured impedance spectra. The W_{ct} elements describe the mass transport in the solid, consisting in finite length diffusion with reflective boundary.^[34,35] Details of the modelling can be found in our previous publications.^[25,34] According to the SEM images (Figure 1), the material is porous and we assume that the pores are completely filled by the solution. We model a pore as an infinite transmission line. According to previous results,^[25] the diffusion in solution is so fast that the corresponding Warburg element can be neglected in the circuit.

The equivalent circuit of Figure 5 reproduces the measured data with good precision, with a relative error of the order of 1%. The Supporting Information describes in detail the error analysis. We avoided over-parametrization by a suitable

Figure 5. Equivalent circuit used for fitting the measured impedance obtained from modelling the ion transfer as a two-stage process in a porous medium. The pore is assumed to be completely filled by the solution and is modelled as an infinite transmission line^[25] (only four elements are shown in the figure as an example). The elements W_{ct} describe the finite length diffusion in the solid.

statistical analysis. Figure S1 of Supporting Information shows that the fitted parameters in the equivalent circuit are significant (i.e., they do not vanish) with more than 95% confidence, thus we are not over-parametrizing the model.

Dependence of the kinetic parameters on the thickness of $LiMn_2O_4$ films

This section reports the discussion of the dependence of the kinetic parameters on the film thickness. The values of the circuit parameters obtained from the fit are reported in Figure 6. The evaluation of the error of the parameters is discussed in the Supporting Information; the relative error is less than 50% for all the parameters (relatively small in the logarithmic scale of Figure 6).

Figure 6a and Figure 6b show the adsorption resistance (R_{ad}) as a function of the occupancy of Li^+ in the interstitial sites of $LiMn_2O_4$ (θ_T). The occupancy θ_T is calculated as a function of the applied potential, based on the integral of the current. Plots of the kinetic parameters versus the electrode potential can be found in Figure S3 and Figure S4 of the Supporting Information.

The result indicates that the dependence of R_{ad} on the occupancy θ_T has a minimum at the two occupancies $\theta_T^A \approx 30\%$ and $\theta_T^B \approx 70\%$, corresponding to the two peak potentials, arising from the insertion of Li^+ into the two solid solutions of $LiMn_2O_4$: this phenomenon is in line with the model

Figure 6. Dependence of the kinetic parameters on the occupancy θ_T . (a, b) Adsorption resistance (R_{ad}) during negative and positive scan, respectively. (c, d) Charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) during negative and positive voltage scan, respectively. (e, f) Warburg coefficient of Li^+ in the $LiMn_2O_4$ lattice (σ_{ct}) during negative and positive voltage scan, respectively.

illustrated in our previous publication.^[25] According to the model, R_{ad} can be expressed as^[25] (Eq. 4):

$$R_{ad} = \frac{RT}{AF^2 k_1^0 \left(\frac{C_{Li^+}}{C_0}\right)^{1-\alpha_1} (1-\beta_1)^{1-\alpha_1} \beta_1^{\alpha_1}} \quad (4)$$

where R is the ideal gas constant, T is the absolute temperature, F is Faraday's constant, C_{Li^+} is the concentration of the lithium ions in the electrolyte, C_0 is the reference concentration (1 M), α_1 is the transfer coefficient of the (de)adsorption step, β_1 represents the occupancy of the adsorbed lithium at the interface (phase l) in each solid solution, A is the surface area, and k_1^0 is the standard rate constant of the (de)adsorption step. The calculation of R_{ad} is reported in detail in the Supporting Information.

As shown in Figure 7a, the value of R_{ad} around the peak potentials do not change significantly with the film thickness. This can be attributed to similarity in k_1^0 and the surface area of the films (A), which is also supported by the relatively small difference in the values of the double-layer capacitance of the films (Figure S2 in the Supporting Information). The hysteresis observed in R_{ad} and other kinetic parameters can be attributed to the influence of concentration of Li^+ in the liquid and at the interface, as well as the diffusion profile during the voltage sweep. This is consistent with kinetic parameters extracted from non-stationary impedance.^[36,37]

Figure 7. Plot of the kinetic parameters at the peak potentials versus film thickness. (a) Adsorption resistance (R_{ad}); (b) charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}); (c) Warburg coefficient of the Li^+ in the $LiMn_2O_4$ (σ_{ct}); (d) mass transport resistance (R_{mt}); (e) total resistance of the film; (f): apparent diffusion path length (l).

The extracted charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) exhibited a dependence on θ_T (Figure 6c and Figure 6d), as shown and explained in our previous paper.^[25] Unlike R_{ad} , the value of R_{ct} at the peak potentials depend on the film thickness, increasing as the film thickness increases (Figure 7b), which is consistent with reports in literature.^[23] As the capacitance of the double layer indicates a similarity in the surface area of the electrodes, the observed differences in R_{ct} can be attributed to different reaction constant k_2^0 in the films. This indicates a drop in k_2^0 with increasing film thickness.

The effect of the film thickness on the mass transport of Li^+ in the $LiMn_2O_4$ films was also investigated. The Warburg coefficient (σ_{ct}) shown in Figure 6e and Figure 6f was observed to have a dependence similar to the shape of the voltammogram as illustrated in our previous publication.^[25] σ_{ct} decreased with increasing film thickness as shown in Figure 7c. As we will discuss later, this is not related to short diffusion paths, since thicker films have longer diffusion paths, but rather to a higher diffusion coefficient of lithium in the $LiMn_2O_4$ particles. It is known that materials with higher crystallinity^[38,39] show higher diffusion coefficient, thus we conclude that the crystallinity increases with the thickness. Summarizing, thicker films are formed by larger crystals with higher crystallinity, showing higher diffusion coefficients. On the other hand, according to the discussion above, k_2^0 decreases with increasing film thickness; if we attribute the variations of k_2^0 to variations of crystallinity, we conclude that the insertion process is facilitated by the presence of defects on the surface.

The above-described analysis gives parameters that have not been yet discussed, in particular the characteristic diffusion time τ . This parameter can be used to further explore the effect of the film thickness on the solid-state mass transport of Li^+ in the films.^[40] We used it to estimate the apparent diffusion path length, l , which corresponds to the distance travelled by lithium-ions in the solid particles, using the following equation (Eq. 5):

$$l \simeq \frac{RT}{AF^2} \frac{4\sqrt{\tau}}{C_T \sigma_{ct}} \quad (5)$$

where C_T is the maximum concentration of lithium in the LMO film (22 mmol cm⁻³). Figure 7f shows the values of l at the peak potentials. The result indicates that the diffusion path length increases as the film thickness increases. This can be attributed to an increase in particle size in the thicker films, resulting in a longer diffusion path length.

Figure 7e shows the total resistance (R_t) of the films defined herein as $R_t = R_{ad} + R_{ct} + R_{mt} + (R_p/3)$, where R_p is the resistance of the pores in the porous electrode model (Figure 5) and R_{mt} is the mass transport resistance defined as $R_{mt} = \sigma_{ct} \sqrt{\tau}/3$, where τ represents the diffusion time constant extracted from the fit.^[25] The result of Figure 7e indicates that the total resistance of the film does increase with increasing film thickness. This can be attributed to the lower mass transport resistance of thicker films (Figure 7d), which compensates for their increased charge transfer resistance. Thus, the poor electrochemical performance of thicker films made by multi-

layer PLD observed at high current rates (104 C)^[41] should be attributed to the longer diffusion paths and longer diffusion time constant (Figure S5 in Supporting Information). The charging of particles with longer diffusion paths with higher charge/discharge currents has been reported to result in structural instability, leading to rapid capacity deterioration.^[42]

The result highlights the role of the film thickness on the kinetic limitation of the various physicochemical phenomena during the Li^+ ion transfer into $LiMn_2O_4$ films made by multi-layer PLD. The resistance of the pores (Figure S4 in Supporting Information) and the mass transport resistance were observed to be the major contributors to the internal resistance of the films. Films with higher crystallinity exhibited lower mass transport resistance, which lowered the total resistance of the films. However, thicker films exhibited a longer diffusion path length due to their increased particle size, which is undesired for cathode materials as longer diffusion path length leads to increased polarization at shorter charge/discharge times. The result provides insights into parameters that can be optimized during film deposition (crystallinity) to improve the electrochemical performance of $LiMn_2O_4$ films made by multi-layer pulsed laser deposition.

Conclusion

In agreement with previous studies,^[25] the ion transfer of Li^+ into $LiMn_2O_4$ films made by pulsed laser deposition follows a two-stage process. In this paper, we compared samples deposited with a different number of pulses, showing different thicknesses and differences in grain size and porosity. The kinetics of the ion transfer is different in the various samples. The adsorption resistance (R_{ad}), which models the (de)adsorption process, is independent of film thickness, while the interfacial and bulk phenomena such as charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}), mass transport resistance in the solid (R_{mt}) and the apparent diffusion path length (l) depended on the film thickness. Thicker films exhibited lower mass transport resistance of Li^+ , thus suggesting the presence of particles with higher crystallinity, which provide a higher diffusion coefficient. The charge transfer resistance increases with increasing film thickness (and thus increasing crystallinity) suggesting that the insertion is more facile in less crystalline films, likely due to the defects. The total resistance of the films indicates that the lower mass transport of the thicker films compensates for their higher charge transfer, resulting in the total resistance not necessarily decreasing with increasing film thickness. However, as the particle size of crystals increases with increasing film thickness, the diffusion path length increases, which results in large polarization at shorter charge/discharge times. The result obtained in this study provides valuable insights into the effect of the film thickness on the kinetic limitation of the physicochemical processes at the interface and the bulk, which can be used in optimizing film deposition to achieve application-optimized electrochemical performances.

Experimental Section

Pulsed laser deposition was carried out on commercial substrates consisting of silicon (10x10 mm) | TiN (10 nm) | Pt (80 nm) in a PLD5000 by PVD Products, Inc. utilizing a Lambda Physik COMPex PRO 205 KrF excimer laser (wavelength $\lambda = 248$ nm, pulse duration 20 ns, maximum power $P = 30$ W, and maximum repetition rate $f = 50$ Hz). The energy of the laser per spot size was fixed by its fluency and calculated to be about 719–830 mJ cm⁻². Deposition conditions were kept constant throughout ablation with 20 mT oxygen background pressure (p_{O_2}) and an oxygen flow of 5 sccm, 10 Hz pulse frequency, 90 mm target-to-substrate distance, and 650°C substrate temperature. Targets of $LiMn_2O_4$ and Li_2O have been purchased from Neyco France, and were constantly alternated within a pulse ratio of 4:3 until a certain amount of pulses was completed. X-ray diffractograms could be collected in a Bruker-D8 Advance operating with Cu-K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.54184$ Å), Ni filter, and Lynx Eye detector. Optical characterization was carried out in a ZEISS AURIGA scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with an InLens detector.

The kinetics of the lithium ion transfer in $LiMn_2O_4$ films was studied in a three-electrode cell set up which comprised the $LiMn_2O_4$ films as the working electrode (WE), a platinum mesh (Labor Platina) as the counter electrode (CE) and a home-made low impedance reference electrode (RE), which reduces or eliminates high-frequency artefacts related to the RE.^[43] The low-impedance reference electrode was fabricated by coiling 0.1 mm platinum wire around the tip of the reference electrode and connecting it through a 100 nF capacitor to the Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl).^[43] The $LiMn_2O_4$ films were investigated in 1 M Li_2SO_4 between 0.4 V to 1.2 V vs Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl), which is well within the stability window of 1 M Li_2SO_4 .^[25] Dynamic multi-frequency analysis was applied by perturbation of the $LiMn_2O_4$ films held at 0.4 V vs Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) with a combined signal composed by a quasi-triangular wave and a multisine waveform. The frequency of the quasi-triangular wave was 10 mHz with an amplitude of 400 mVpp corresponding to a scan rate of 16 mVs⁻¹. This scan rate is appropriate for investigating LMO films made by multi-layer PLD as shown in our previous papers,^[25] where the separation between anodic and cathodic peaks, remains small in comparable cycling rate.^[44] The multisine comprised 45 frequencies covering six decades with a base frequency of 0.5 Hz and an amplitude of 100 mVpp which translated to dynamic impedance been acquired within the frequency range of 500 kHz to 0.5 Hz. The current response indicates that the system is linear for the 100 mVpp amplitude as shown in Supporting Information of our previous publication.^[25] The current range of the VS-300 Bio-Logic potentiostat was set at 100 mA. The voltage perturbation and the output current were recorded using a two-channel oscilloscope 4262 PicoScope (Pico technology). 4000 impedance spectra were extracted from the 400 million samples collected at a time interval of 500 ns with a home-written MATLAB script, using one of the descriptions of dynamic impedance^[28,45] (Eq. 6):

$$Z' = \frac{iFT[\Delta U(\omega) \cdot g(\omega' - \omega), bw]}{iFT[\Delta I(\omega) \cdot g(\omega' - \omega), bw]} \quad (6)$$

where ΔU and ΔI are the Fourier transform of the potential and current signals respectively, ω is the angular frequency, g is a quadrature filter function, and bw is the bandwidth of the quadrature filter.^[27,45] The impedance spectra shown in this paper contained 40 frequencies from 210 kHz to 2.5 Hz of the 45 frequencies. The other frequencies from 500 kHz to 281 kHz and 1.5 Hz to 0.5 Hz were discarded due to high-frequency artefacts and noise as explained in our previous publication,^[25] while

artefacts arising from the non-ideal behaviour of the voltage and current amplifier (I/E converters) and stray capacitance was corrected using the method reported in Ref.^[46]

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords: dynamic impedance spectroscopy · interfacial lithium-ion transfer · LiMn_2O_4 thin films · multi-frequency analysis · multi-layer pulsed laser deposition

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